

ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION BY PLASTIC WASTE

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Abstract: *The article deals with some issues of plastic waste formation in Azerbaijan, which belong to the category of hazardous waste. In particular, it is said that plastic waste contains dangerous particles and has a detrimental effect on all living things. In the article, the issues of the scale of these wastes are also discussed, a brief information is given - an overview of undesirable situations of the influence of waste pollution on the health of the population. It is recommended to be more responsible for the utilization of all plastic waste.*

Key words: *plastic waste, microplastic, ecosystem, disposal, recycling, toxins.*

The spread of plastic materials in soils and their impact on living organisms. The damage plastic waste causes to aquatic ecosystems in the seas and oceans is well known. On land, plastic pollution is less widely discussed. According to experts from the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the scale of the problem of plastic pollution of land is very large and has not yet been fully assessed [1].

Only a small part of the plastic that is thrown into our environment every day is incinerated industrially or recycled for energy. The vast majority of this waste is dumped in landfills. It takes up to a thousand years for plastic waste to completely decompose. Most plastic waste breaks down into particles smaller than 5 mm. These particles are called “microplastics”. They are then broken down into nanoparticles.

During the decomposition process, toxic substances can leak into the soil and water. They can move through the soil, sediments and water sources and negatively affect these ecosystems. According to numerous studies, microplastic particles are everywhere.

According to several sources [2,3,4], soil pollution with microplastics is higher than that in the oceans. In some cases, depending on the environment, the pollution can be more than 20 times.

In most cases, these particles enter the human digestive system, accumulate and play a negative role. Microplastics also have a significant impact on running water and groundwater. On the other hand, wastewater collected in treatment plants is used as fertilizer in agricultural work. Thus, a large amount of plastic particles remain in the soil. At the same time, they affect the quality and fertility of the soil. Soil pollution with plastics has also led to a decrease in the number of underground fauna that maintain its productivity.

In general, plastic pollution affects living organisms through physical, chemical and habitat destruction. Physical effects include ingestion, entanglement, and suffocation. Chemical effects include the release of toxins from plastic, the absorption of poisons, and habitat destruction, which can lead to various diseases, reduced reproductive function, and overall ecosystem disruption.

One type of plastic is polyvinyl chloride. This plastic releases harmful chemicals into the soil. These substances can enter groundwater or other surrounding water sources. Thus, they can cause a number of potentially harmful effects on all living things that use water.

Other elements - phthalates and bisphenol - are also known for their effects on the hormonal system of living organisms. These additives leach plastic particles into the soil. Nanoparticles of these elements can cause an inflammatory process. They can cause changes in gene expression and biochemical reactions of the cell, and can even penetrate the brain, blood-brain barrier, and cell membranes. The long-term effects of these changes are not yet well studied.

The most dangerous types of plastic

Which plastic is the most dangerous, which can be used and which should be completely avoided?

1. Polypropylene/PP is used to make juice containers for children, leak-proof bottles for babies, and containers for baby food.

2. High-density polyethylene is used to make containers for milk and other food products. They can be used several times. However, they are capable of releasing formaldehydes. Formaldehydes have a negative effect on the respiratory and nervous systems.

3. Polyethylene terephthalate is used to make containers for water, drinks, vegetable oil, and sauces. It is recommended not to reuse these containers. Because reuse can release phthalates. Phthalates have a negative effect on the nervous, endocrine, and reproductive systems.

4. Polystyrene is a material for the production of disposable knives, spoons, forks, egg trays, cups, foam, and boxes for discs. Products made of polystyrene can be used only once. When reused, heated or decomposed, styrene is released. Styrene has a negative effect on the circulatory, nervous systems, as well as the liver and kidneys.

5. Polyvinyl chloride is used to make furniture, food containers and film, windows, suspended ceilings and children's toys. It has a very negative effect on the human body.

6. Low-density polyethylene is used for bags for household chemicals and equipment. It releases formaldehyde during decomposition and heating. Otherwise it is harmless.

Cleaning of soils from plastic substances.

Cleaning of soils from pollution with plastic materials is carried out by various methods. All these methods are of varying degrees of complexity. However, given their complexity, it can be said with confidence that this problem requires complex approaches on a large scale. The main methods include the following:

- removal of large plastic fragments from the soil;
- thermal processing of plastic to decompose it;
- physical and chemical methods;
- biological methods for the decomposition or accumulation of plastics in the soil.

The latter method is called bioremediation. This method uses microorganisms or plants.

Cleaning methods:

Physical methods:

- removal of large pieces of plastic contaminants from the soil;
- using special materials to remove large plastic fragments from the soil;

• Chemical methods:

- washing of soils with water and aqueous solutions to remove various chemicals from the soil.

Biological methods:

- use of microorganisms and plants;
- sorption-biological methods (to reduce the content of petroleum products and other pollutants).

Thermal methods:

- heat treatment in furnaces at high temperatures to remove organic pollutants.

Soil replacement:

- In exceptional cases, it may be necessary to completely remove and replace the contaminated soil layer.

At the same time, scientists and experts, companies and universities around the world are looking for more efficient, more useful methods for cleaning soils from plastic and microplastic pollution. For example, German experts [5] have found an environmentally friendly and clean way to clean soil contaminated with microplastics with the help of trees. It is known that microplastic particles can be absorbed by plants. Even microplastics are absorbed, including in the vegetables and fruits we eat. Based on other studies, microplastic particles accumulate in the root systems of plants and cause problems for root crops. In turn, this situation opens up the possibility of using plants to remove microplastics from the ecosystem in a controlled manner.

Thus, IGB experts [5] have shown for the first time that the roots of silver birch trees absorb microplastics during growth. Considering that soils are many times more polluted with microplastics than the oceans, this result is promising.

The use of this type of plant has been studied as a way to clean contaminated soils from microplastics. Silver maple roots grow close to the soil surface, where microplastic contamination is highest. This makes them a good choice for research.

The researchers added microplastic particles labeled with fluorescent dyes to the soil of silver maples planted in special pots. After five months, the silver maple root systems were examined using laser microscopy. It was found that microplastics made up between 5 and 17% of the silver maple roots.

Pollution of the environment with plastic materials, including, and mainly, packaging products, has become a major problem in the last fifty years. This problem has now become global and urgently needs to be solved. A large amount of various types of plastic waste has accumulated in almost all elements of the biosphere - in water, soil and atmospheric air. And this process continues rapidly every moment, further exacerbating the problem under consideration. The problem is that the resistance of this plastic material to biodegradation in soil and water is great. These wastes can remain in soil and water as a pollutant for a period of time equal to a human lifetime. Such a situation has a negative impact on all ecosystems, all living things and even the climate of our planet. Finding effective ways to process and dispose of plastic material, developing and applying science-based methods by scientists and specialists has become one of the most important tasks in the field of environmental protection. There is a need to find solutions to reduce the amount of waste from plastic materials and drastically reduce their impact on the environment. The development of modern and progressive technologies for the processing of plastic materials is a key factor in solving this global environmental problem. The economic and social impacts of plastic pollution require urgent action. Therefore, the development of the field of processing plastic waste is not only an ecological, but also an economic necessity.

For many years, plastic pollution of soils has become a serious environmental problem in many countries. When such waste enters the soil, it breaks down into microplastics, which can produce harmful chemicals that can harm the environment and human health. These particles are smaller than five millimeters. These, in turn, then break down into even smaller nanoparticles. Their size is less than 0.1 micrometers. Information about how much plastic pollution harms the environment in general is regularly disseminated by the world scientific community. Basically, such information is more common for the world's oceans. However, information about plastic pollution of soils is relatively less.

According to experts from the United Nations Environment Program, the scale of the problem of plastic soil pollution is huge [1]. Toxic substances enter the soil and water, polluting them for many years. More precisely, in fact, this problem has not yet been fully assessed. Discarded plastic is burned industrially and electricity is obtained from it. The rest is recycled. And it takes hundreds and thousands of years for this waste to completely decompose.

According to researchers, soil pollution with microparticles is estimated to be more serious than water pollution. Depending on the state of the environment, it is estimated to be 20 times more serious [1]. Plastic microparticles found in the environment can have a negative impact on the ecosystem as a whole. It should be noted that plastic particles can be found all over the world. These particles enter the human body through food and accumulate there.

Pros, cons and advantages of plastic materials.

Plastic products are widely used due to their positive properties and affordable price.

Products made of plastic materials have high strength. Products made of plastic materials can withstand heavy loads. They have a number of properties:

- light weight;
- easy processing;
- aesthetic appearance;

- good heat and sound insulation;
- the possibility of recycling and reuse.

As for the disadvantages of products made of plastic materials, it should be noted that they are not suitable for use at high temperatures. As the temperature increases, plastic begins to melt, and as it cools, it becomes brittle and cracks

In conclusion, we can say that although plastic products are cheap and convenient, and make people's lives easier, they also cause serious damage to the environment. In addition, it is important to take special responsibility when choosing plastic products that will be used for children or for food products. It is necessary to approach the use of plastic materials consciously.

Distribution of plastic materials in the environment.

Part of the plastic waste is taken to specially designed landfills. The other, even larger part of it, often ends up in the environment in various ways. This waste enters the soil, rivers, lakes, seas and oceans in the form of large-sized garbage. On the other hand, this waste breaks down and spreads in these objects in the form of smaller particles. Their sizes are so small that they are called microparticles. Such particles enter ecosystems and have a devastating effect on the health of all living organisms. It should be emphasized that since plastic materials are durable, it takes hundreds of years for them to completely decompose. During this time, they accumulate and release toxic substances. As a result, respectively, flora and fauna are seriously damaged, and then enter the food chain.

The distribution of plastic materials in the environment occurs on land, in water bodies and in sewers. Plastic accumulated in landfills breaks down into garbage and microparticles. Then they seep into the soil and groundwater (Figure 1). At the same time, some of them are transported over considerable distances by wind and rain.

A significant part of plastic substances (garbage) ends up in rivers, seas and oceans. As a result, huge and variously sized garbage islands are formed in the oceans. Some of these islands are visible even from space.

Some of the plastic substances (garbage) also end up in sewers. These materials - synthetic detergents, personal hygiene products, etc.

Therefore, the accumulation of plastic waste has serious consequences for nature, ecosystems and human health.

Thus, despite the above, plastic pollution comes from various sources, covering both land and sea activities. It is necessary to develop effective strategies to prevent this pollution. This, in turn, requires an understanding of the sources of pollution. Some of the main sources of plastic pollution are disposable plastic bags, water containers of various sizes, plastic objects, etc. These have a significant negative impact on environmental pollution when discarded.

Another reason for plastic pollution is improper disposal of waste. In this regard, garbage and illegal dumps cause this type of waste to enter the environment.

Another reason for plastic pollution is the production of plastic itself. Thus, plastic waste is also generated during mining operations

Fig.1 Ways plastic gets into the soil.

The following reasons

- excessive use of various plastic containers;
- microplastic particles formed during the washing process of synthetic materials and then entering the environment;
- industrial facilities emit plastic particles and pollutants into the water during their activities;
- urban sewage networks carry plastic waste to water bodies;
- fishing gear of fishermen remains in the seas, etc.

In general, it should be said that the study and investigation of various sources of pollution is very important for the development of comprehensive strategies in this area in the future. Action in this area is crucial for developing comprehensive strategies to reduce plastic use, improve waste management practices, and reduce the environmental impact of plastic.

The impact of plastic materials on the environment. After plastic enters the environment, new problems come to the fore. The main and most important problem is the problem of environmental pollution by plastic materials. This problem is a complex and multifaceted problem. The daily use of plastic materials has become one of the most urgent environmental problems of our century. A huge amount of plastic waste is generated in the world every year. This indicates that the impact on the Earth is large and multifaceted. Plastics penetrate every corner of the world: soils, waters and the air we breathe are polluted. Therefore, the accumulation of plastic waste has serious consequences for ecosystems and human health [2,5,6].

This problem is already putting people in a state of crisis. Solving this plastic crisis requires a multifaceted approach. Multifacetedness requires certain changes in world politics and technological innovations.

Therefore, it needs to be analyzed in detail. As products made of plastic materials decompose, they pose a threat to the ecosystem, including soil fertility. Microplastics can remain in the soil for hundreds of years. These are washed into the soil with toxic substances such as Bisphenol A (BPA) and phthalates. These chemicals have hormonal effects on all living organisms. They can also cause inflammation.

Plastic pollution has a very serious impact on the soil. According to some researchers, microplastic pollution in soils is greater than that in the oceans and seas [6]. The presence of microplastics in the soil can change their physical and chemical properties. This affects plant vegetation and the health of soil microbiology.

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